

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTETHIS AND ANALYSIS OF ZINC OXIDES NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using the sol-gel method. optimal conditions for the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles were developed using various environmentally friendly reducing agents and reaction media. The structure of the obtained materials containing a finely dispersed metal phase has been studied, and the size of metal particles in the volume and on the surface of the obtained material has been determined. Based on the results of the study, these synthesized compounds were recommended as bioinhibitors against microorganisms.

Keywords: nanoparticles, zinc oxide, scanning electron microscopy, spectrometry.

ZnO nanoparticles are considered one of the three most produced nanomaterials, along with titanium dioxide nanoparticles and silicon dioxide nanoparticles. Most often, ZnO nanoparticles are used in sunscreens. They are used because they effectively absorb ultraviolet light, but have a band gap large enough to be completely transparent to visible light. They are also being tested for the destruction of harmful microorganisms in packaging and in UV protection materials such as textiles. Based on the highly efficient and promising properties of zinc oxide nanoparticles, it was concluded that it is necessary to synthesize and study these compounds [1].

The chemical system in the sol-gel method consists of three main components - a precursor, a solvent, and a stabilizer. In the sol-gel process, the molecular precursor in a homogeneous solution undergoes a sequence of transformations: hydrolysis, polymerization

by sequential bimolecular addition of ions with the formation of oxo-, hydroxyl or aqua-bridges. condensation by dehydration, nucleation and growth [2]. The solvent must have a relatively high dielectric constant to dissolve the inorganic salts. Most alcohols fulfill this condition. Alcohols with low carbon numbers up to 4 are the most used solvents: methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 2-propanol, 1-butanol and 2-methoxyethanol. Additives are chemical compounds that have at least one functional group, which allows these compounds to play multiple roles. They act as a basic or acidic and/or chelating agent. For this, alkali metal hydroxides, carboxylic acids, alkanolamines, alkylamines, acetylacetone and polyalcohols are used. They can contribute to the dissolution of the zinc salt in some alcohol environments. Based on the collected data, the initial substances for the synthesis of nanoparticles were selected [3,4].

Table 1

Characteristics of the chemicals used in the work

Substance name	Chemical formula	Molecule model
1	2	3
Zinc acetate dihydrate	$\left[\text{H}_3\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{O}^- \right]_2 \text{Zn}^{2+} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	
Sodium hydroxide	$\text{Na}-\text{O}-\text{H}$	
Liquid glass	$\text{Na}^+ \overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}} \text{Na}^+$ O^-	
Ethanol	$\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \text{H} \\ \quad \\ \text{H}-\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{OH} \\ \quad \\ \text{H} \quad \text{H} \end{array}$	

The purpose of this study is to establish the patterns of formation of zinc oxide nanoparticles in ethyl solutions, and to obtain zinc oxide nanoparticles. A series of experiments was carried out in alcoholic solutions. To achieve the goal, the following tasks were solved: - determination of the nature of the influence of various factors (concentrations of reagents, temperature, stabilizing additives) on the formation of zinc oxide nanoparticles; - search for optimal conditions for the synthesis of stable zinc oxide hydrosols, including concentrated ones; The ratio of their concentrations was established by varying the volumes of reagent solutions. A fiber sample 100 × 100 mm in size, after determining the exact mass on an analytical balance, was

A dispersion of zinc oxide nanoparticles was obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of zinc acetate in ethanol. First dissolve the zinc acetate (in this method the concentration of zinc acetate varies) in ethanol by heating in a laboratory shaker. At the same time, 50 ml (total ml of ethanol is 100 ml) of ethanol was placed in the flask. When the zinc acetate was completely dissolved, 50 ml of chilled ethanol was added to the solution. Sodium hydroxide was also dissolved in ethanol alcohol

impregnated with an aqueous solution of zinc oxide nanoparticles on a laboratory two-shaft padding with 90% extraction, and drying and heat treatment were carried out on needle frames in a drying cabinet with a thermostat. After drying and heat treatment, the sample was washed in distilled water and then dried at room temperature. Before carrying out the experimental work, the unseamed flax fiber was preliminarily washed in distilled water to remove residues of various impurities, dried, and kept in a desiccator with a calcium chloride desiccant to determine the exact weight. The method for obtaining zinc oxide nanoparticles was based on the method of precipitation from solution during the following chemical reaction:

(0.05 M) and cooled in an ice bath, and then an aqueous solution of zinc acetate was added dropwise to the solution with constant stirring. In this way, ZnO was obtained. The dressed and undressed fiber was sent for analysis to the nanotechnological laboratory at Al-Farabi Kazakh State University for subsequent identification of the resulting nanoparticles using a Quanta 3D 200i Dual system Field Emission Scanning Scanning Electron Microscope.

Fig.1. Photographs of the finished sample with a resolution of a) 200 μm b) 50 μm

The optical densities of the reaction solutions were also determined using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer with Agilent Cary 60, G6860A software.

Table 2

Optical density of solutions at wavelengths of 100-500nm				
Wavelength, nm	Optical density at 0.01M	Optical density at 0.02M	Optical density at 0.03M	Optical density at 0.04M
100	0,238	0,456	0,635	0,678
150	0,245	0,568	0,759	0,763
200	0,564	0,675	0,987	0,987
250	0,978	0,814	1,131	1,124
300	1,34	1,545	1,976	2,563
350	1,231	1,654	2,053	2,345
400	0,956	1,435	1,876	1,828
450	0,678	1,128	1,433	1,332
500	0,435	0,876	1,115	0,901

Pic.2. Wavelength to absorbance diagram

A method has been developed for modifying cellulose fabrics using sol-gel synthesis, using sodium hydroxide, sodium silicate with the addition of zinc acetate, which provides effective antimicrobial activity of the textile material. The method of modifying materials is universal, accessible and simple in execution.

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